

Supplementary Table 2: Selected features for the best solutions for differential diagnosis of AD and bvFTD, and PPA, with classifiers *BayesNet Naives (NB)* and *K-Nearest-Neighbor (KNN)*. Features are presented in alphabetical order.

Classifier	Features
AD vs HC	
KNN	Angular L, Angular R, Calcarine R, Cerebellum 10 R, Cerebellum 3 L, Cerebellum 4 5 R, Cerebellum 6 L, Cerebellum 7b L, Cerebellum 8 L, Cerebellum 8 R, CingulumPost R, Frontal Inf Oper R, Frontal Inf Orb L, Frontal Inf Tri L, Frontal Med Orb R, Frontal Mid Orb L, Frontal Sup Orb R, Heschl R, Hippocampus L, Precentral R, Precuneus L, Precuneus R, Putamen R, Rectus R, TemporalInf L, TemporalPole Mid R, TemporalPole Sup R, TemporalSup R, Thalamus L, Thalamus R, Vermis 4 5
NB	Angular L, Calcarine L, Calcarine R, Cerebellum 10 R, Cerebellum 8 R, CingulumMid R, Cuneus L, Occipital Inf R, Olfactory L, ParietalSup L, TemporalSup L, Thalamus R
bvFTD vs HC	
KNN	Cerebellum 9 R, CingulumAnt L, CingulumMid R, Frontal Inf Oper R, Frontal Sup Orb L, Occipital Mid L, Pallidum R, ParietalSup L, Precentral L, Rectus R, TemporalPole Mid L, Vermis 6, Vermis 8
NB	CingulumAnt L, Frontal Inf Oper R, Occipital Mid L, ParietalSup L, TemporalSup L
bvFTD vs AD	
KNN	Amygdala R, Caudate L, Cerebellum 10 L, Cerebellum 3 R, Cerebellum 7b L, Cerebellum Crus1 L, Cerebellum Crus1 R, CingulumPost R, Cuneus R, Frontal Inf Oper L, Frontal Med Orb L, Frontal Mid L, Frontal Mid Orb R, Frontal Sup Orb L, Frontal Sup Orb R, Fusiform R, Occipital Mid R, Occipital Sup R, Olfactory R, Pallidum L, ParietalInf L, Rolandic Oper L, TemporalPole Mid R, TemporalPole Sup R, Thalamus L
NB	Frontal Inf Oper L, Frontal Inf Orb L, Frontal Inf Orb R, Occipital Inf L, Occipital Sup L, ParietalInf R, ParietalSup R, Putamen R, TemporalInf R, TemporalPole Mid L, TemporalSup L, Thalamus R
PPA (differential diagnosis between different variants and HCs)	
KNN	Amygdala L, Calcarine R, Cerebellum 8 L, Cerebellum 8 R, Frontal Inf Oper L, Frontal Inf Oper R, Frontal Inf Orb L, Frontal Inf Orb R, Frontal Mid L, Frontal Mid Orb R, Frontal Mid R, Frontal Sup L, Frontal Sup R, Fusiform L, Fusiform R, Lingual R, Occipital Inf R, Occipital Mid R, Pallidum L, SMA L, SMA R, TemporalMid R, TemporalPole Mid R, TemporalPole Sup L, Vermis 10
NB	Calcarine L, Caudate R, Cerebellum Crus2 L, Cuneus R, Frontal Inf Tri L, Heschl R, Insula L, Occipital Inf R, Parahippocamp L, Parahippocamp R, Precentral L, Putamen L, Rectus R, SMA R, Supramarginal R, TemporalMid R, TemporalPole Mid R, TemporalPole Sup L, Thalamus L, Vermis 1 2, Vermis 8